

Obs4MIPs Data Specifications

ODS2.6.1

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For the latest obs4MIPs tables and controlled vocabulary, please see the dedicated Github repository: <https://github.com/PCMDI/obs4MIPs-cmor-tables/tree/master>

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Introduction

The purpose of [obs4MIPs](#) is to facilitate comparison of gridded and un-gridded observational data with model output from WCRP intercomparison projects, notably the [Coupled Model Intercomparison Project \(CMIP\)](#). To accomplish this, the organisation and description of CMIP and obs4MIPs data are closely coordinated, as described in this document. The details of this technical alignment, including the data structure and metadata requirements, facilitate coordinated delivery via the [Earth System Grid Federation \(ESGF\)](#) and use of the data for model evaluation, research, and development.

The original obs4MIPs contributions followed CMIP5 data specification guidelines (ca. 2012, hereafter ODS1.0). This early phase was challenging because the software infrastructure ([CMOR](#)) did not readily accommodate observations. This was rectified in CMIP6, with the obs4MIPs team working closely with the [Working Group on Coupled Models \(WGCM\) Infrastructure Panel \(WIP\)](#) aligning ODS2.1 to [CMIP6 data specifications](#). At that time, obs4MIPs coordination and governance was provided by the WCRP's Data Advisory Council's (WDAC) Observations for Model Evaluation Task Team. Since 2022 this role has been fulfilled by the WIP and the obs4MIPs Steering Panel with technical support of the [CMIP International Project Office \(CMIP IPO\)](#) and oversight of [WCRP's ESMO](#).

To avoid naming conflicts in the identification of data sources and institutions, data providers must register the name of their institution and other information about their data *prior to generating* obs4MIPs data sets. This process is analogous to CMIP and is done by submitting a Registered Content (RC) issue on the [obs4MIPs-cmor-tables Github repository](#). [Appendix 2](#) details the information required.

All obs4MIPs-compliant datasets are either prepared by the official data curator, or a third-party. Either way, the institution providing a obs4MIPs-compliant dataset is identified via the <variant_label> attribute (See Table 1). Third-party contributors have to inform the original curators that they are preparing an obs4MIPs-compliant version of their data product, and honour licensing associated with the original data.

Efforts are underway to develop a “validator” or “checker”, to confirm whether or not a dataset is obs4MIPs-compliant and technically structured to be consistent with CMIP output even if it was prepared without using CMOR. To meet the strict requirements of aligning model

and observational data, this includes not just adhering to the metadata conventions, but also the structure and type of the data including all coordinates and bounds. If a mechanism to confirm a dataset is “CMOR equivalent” is established, the requirement of using CMOR for obs4MIPs may be relaxed to “recommended”. Already, if a particular dataset cannot be prepared with CMOR for technical reasons, it can be prepared with other methods provided the ODS specifications are met, the data closely matches CMIP model output, and the processing scripts are included in the obs4MIPs-cmor-tables GitHub repository.

Obs4MIPs metadata specifications for the following categories are described in this document:

1. [Global attributes](#): Explicitly defined metadata included in netCDF files that describe the contents of the dataset and provenance (e.g., <source_id>).
2. [Data Reference Syntax \(DRS\)](#): Some attributes (e.g., <institution_id>, <source_id>, <variable_id>) comprise the data reference syntax (DRS) for obs4MIPs, which closely parallels the DRS of CMIP6. The DRS is used in file names, directory structures, and facets of some search tools such as ESGF.
3. [Directory structure](#): This includes selected DRS information used as subdirectories. As per CMIP6, it is explicitly defined in obs4MIPs to facilitate organization of a federated database and searching for data with ESGF.
4. [Filenames](#): Like the directory structure, filenames are constructed based on a template that uses Controlled Variables (CV) entries.

This document includes a discussion of the inclusion (or not) of grid cell bounds. These bounds make it possible for users of the data to weigh the influence of each cell based on its surface area (or volume), for calculating a domain mean. A user can estimate the grid cell bounds, but those closest to the original data are generally best positioned to construct, estimate, or consider bounds for a particular dataset to be poorly defined and therefore not included. We recommend that data providers include grid bounds ([Appendix 1](#)).

What is new in ODS2.6?

The standards describing CMIP data are quite mature, with the general structure not changing significantly from one phase to the next of CMIP. ODS2.6 includes minor changes to ODS2.5 while retaining consistency with existing (CMIP6) protocols. Minor updates to ODS2.6 may be required as the data protocols of CMIP7 are established. Making changes to ODS where necessary ensures continuity and backward compatibility. The main changes since ODS2.5 are summarised here and described later in this document.

Changes to obs4MIPs Global Attributes, DRS, filenames, and directory structure

- **New global attributes: <aux_uncertainty_id>, <has_aux_unc>, <DOI>, <site_id> and <site_location> (see Table 1)**
- **Guidelines for inclusion of (single and multi) site data, with new <product> options (Appendix 3)**
- **Guidelines for the inclusion of uncertainty information as separate but related files (Appendix 5)**
- **Guidelines for the provision of anomaly fields (Appendix 6)**
- **Provision for statistical/uncertainty information and anomalies via <variable_id> suffixes**
- **The filename template, directory template, and DRS in ODS2.6 is identical to ODS2.5**

Global attributes

The global attributes facilitate organisation of the obs4MIPs datasets, in particular providing useful options (or facets) for data exploration via [ESGF metagrid](#). DRS is more behind the scenes than the search functions - but is critical in defining how data from the CMIP and obs4MIPs

databases are organised (notably the directory structure). These obs4MIPs data structures are curated by the authors of this document in coordination with the obs4MIPs Steering Panel and the WIP.

CMIP data requirements are currently facilitated by using the [Climate Model Output Rewriter](#) (CMOR), recommended for producing obs4MIPs-compliant datasets, because the necessary metadata for ESGF distributed data searching is included. [Following instructions](#), a user populates an input table with the entries of the required global attributes, and data is read in (via a python script) and output via CMOR, which automatically produces the DRS and file names.

Table 1 contains the list of obs4MIPs global attributes, indicating which are required and which are optional. The values for many of the global attributes must be drawn from special obs4MIPs controlled vocabularies (CVs). A CV is a list of the permitted values that can be assigned to a given global attribute. The lists of permitted values can be found in the [Github repository](#)

Table 1: obs4MIPs global attribute description

obs4MIPs global attributes see note 1	Description	Examples	Introduced	Form see note 2	Required	Further information
aux_uncertainty_id	Suffix added to variable_id to indicates statistical uncertainty quantity	"sd" (Standard deviation) "stderr" (Standard error), "ucom" (Common uncertainty), "uind" (Independent uncertainty), "ustr" (Structured uncertainty) see also Appendix 5 table	NEW IN ODS2.6	Should be considered controlled vocabulary.	when has_aux_unc is TRUE	Can be used to query if uncertainty data is available/ associated
	activity identifier	only value permitted is	originally	CV	always	Renamed more generically,

obs4MIPs global attributes see note 1	Description	Examples	Introduced	Form see note 2	Required	Further information
activity_id see note 3		“obs4MIPs”	project_id in ODS1.0			since not all activities are projects; multiple activities may now be listed separated by single spaces
comment	see note 9	see note 9	ODS1.0	free form	optional	No change from original obs4MIPs or CMIP5; CF-convention standard
contact	see note 9	see note 9	ODS1.0	free form	always	Still required with ODS-2.6
Conventions	convention version	" CF-1.11 ODS-2.6"	ODS1.0	CVs	always	Updated version from ODS-1.0 with a list of conventions separated by single spaces now allowed
creation_date	date file was created	see note 5	ODS1.0	structured form	always	No change from original obs4MIPs specs (automatic with CMOR3)
dataset_contributor	Identifies the individual who obtained the original data and made it obs4MIPs-compliant	Initials or full name contributor	ODS2.5	free form	always	Helps make the process of preparing obs4MIPs-compliant data fully traceable
data_specs_version	version identifier of obs4MIPs CVs and CMOR tables	e.g. 2.6	ODS2.1	CVs	always	This version number is associated with the version or GitHub “tag” for the obs4MIPs

obs4MIPs global attributes see note 1	Description	Examples	Introduced	Form see note 2	Required	Further information
						CMOR tables and the CVs. See PCMDI/obs4MIPs-cmor-tables which originate from the CMIP6 tables
doi	DOI of original dataset	10.15770/EUM_SAF_OSI_0023	NEW IN ODS2.6	structured form	encouraged	DOI pointing to the source of dataset
external_variables	external cell measures	“areacella”, “areacello”, “volcella”, “volcello”, as defined in CMIP6	ODS2.1	CVs	rarely needed, but include when appropriate	List of cell-measured variables (separated by single spaces) that are referenced but not included in the file. These variables will be stored independently in the obs4MIPs data archive. Use of this attribute is expected to be infrequent in contrast to the recommended inclusion of grid bounds (Appendix 1)
frequency	sampling frequency	“mon”	ODS1.0	CV	always	No change from original obs4MIPs. The current options are given in obs4MIPs_frequency.json
grid	grid, In the case of in situ observations this should be set to ‘site’ or ‘site-collection’	see note 7 ,	ODS2.1	free form	always	Briefly describes output grid characteristics

obs4MIPs global attributes see note 1	Description	Examples	Introduced	Form see note 2	Required	Further information
grid_label	grid identifier used in filename. In the case of in situ observations this should be set to 'site-' + site_id or 'site-collection'.	"gn", "gr1", see note 8 Site examples: "site-SGP", "site-collection"	ODS2.1	CVs (note 8)	always	Used in file name to distinguish among files when the variable is reported on more than one grid. See obs4MIPs_grid_label.json
has_aux_unc	Flag for existence of uncertainty data	TRUE or FALSE	NEW IN ODS2.6	structured form	always	set to TRUE when additional files containing uncertainty information are provided. It should be set to FALSE when no uncertainty information is provided
history	see note 9	see note 9	ODS1.0	free form	optional	No change; CF-convention standard
institution	institution name	"NOAA's National Centers for Environmental Information, Asheville, NC 28801, USA"	ODS1.0	CV with registered content	always	Can be used to identify institute responsible for dataset including a curator role if data is no longer managed by original individual or entity. It can also be used to identify institution of a "3rd party" contributor. These entries must be registered in: obs4MIPs_institution_id.json
institution_id	institution identifier	"NCEI"	ODS1.0	CV with	always	Formerly "institute_id";

obs4MIPs global attributes see note 1	Description	Examples	Introduced	Form see note 2	Required	Further information
ESGF alias institute_id for backwards compatibility with ODS v1.0				registered content		attribute name changed to align with CMIP. This string is constructed only using the character set: a-z, A-Z, 0-9, and "-". These entries must be registered on the GitHub repo
license	license restrictions	see note 13	ODS2.1	licence text	always	Ensures that anyone using the files has access to the terms of use
long_name	A long descriptive name that could be used for labelling plots. If not given, default is variable_id	E.g. "global-mean surface temperature", or "change in global-mean surface temperature relative to pre-industrial" See Appendix 6	NEW IN ODS2.6	Structured form	As appropriate	For anomaly datasets See the CF Conventions documentation Section 3.1
nominal_resolution	approximate horizontal resolution or "site" or "site-collection" when in-situ data.	"50 km", "100 km", "250 km", "1x1 degree", "site", "site-collection" (See Appendix 2 of CMIP6 specifications)	ODS2.1	CV	always	Added in CMIP6 to provide an indication of approximate output grid resolution. See obs4MIPs_nominal_resolution.json
processing_code_location	Direct link to code used to process data via GitHub	When preparing data via GH repo, a function can be called that	ODS2.5		always	Ensures transparency in the processing of obs4MIPs-compliant data by pointing to

obs4MIPs global attributes see note 1	Description	Examples	Introduced	Form see note 2	Required	Further information
	hashtag	identifies the precise code version which can be saved as a global attribute. See provenance info in demo				the processing code (using CMOR) from which it was prepared.
product	product type	“derived”, “observations”, “site-observations”, “site-collection”, “reanalysis”,	ODS1.0		always	As in original obs4MIPs and CMIP5. Site-observations introduced for ODS 2.6
realm	realm(s) where variable is defined	“atmos”, “ocean”, “land”, “sealce” “atmosChem”	ODS1.0	CV	always	As in original obs4MIPs. See obs4MIPs_realm.json
references	see note 9	see note 9	ODS1.0	free form	always	No change; CF-convention standard
region	Pre-defined (CF conventions) approximate regions	“north_america”, “global”, “global_land” (multiple entries ok)	ODS2.1	CV (list content)	always	See obs4MIPs_region.json
site_id	Name for the in-situ measurement location if individual	“AU-Rob”, “CA-Gro”, “collection”,	NEW in ODS2.6	CV	as required	See example site demo on the Github repository

obs4MIPs global attributes see note 1	Description	Examples	Introduced	Form see note 2	Required	Further information
	site and “collection” if multiple sites. In the case of gridded data.					
site_location	Location of the in-situ measurement site if individual site and “collection” if multiple sites. In the case of gridded data.	“Robson Creek, Queensland, Australia”, “Ontario, “Groundhog River, Boreal mixed wood Forest”, “collection”,	NEW in ODS2.6	CV	as required	As above
source (modified form)	full observational dataset name/version	see Appendix 2	ODS2.1	CV (Generated from registered content)	always	More comprehensive than original obs4MIPs and CMIP5. See Tables/obs4MIPs_CV.json and search for “source_id”
source_id (modified form)	Unique identifier for dataset	“GPCP-2-4-1” See Appendix 2	ODS1.0	CV (Generated from registered content)	always	Edited version of first part of “source” (with forbidden characters like spaces and periods replaced with hyphens); used in constructing the file name. See obs4MIPs_source_id.json for examples

obs4MIPs global attributes see note 1	Description	Examples	Introduced	Form see note 2	Required	Further information
source_data_notes	Can be used to provide additional information on the accessibility of source data.		ODS2.5		optional	This attribute can be used to highlight any technical details regarding how the data were retrieved, e.g., via a script or manual download.
source_data_retrieval_date	Provides the date the dataset preparer retrieved the data from the original source.	e.g., "2025-03-23T05:56:23Z"	ODS2.5	See note 5	encouraged	Helps ensure the version of the original data is clearly identified
source_data_url	URL location where source data was retrieved (normally a recognized curator of the data)		ODS2.5		encouraged	Pointer to the original data. Helps improve version control transparency
source_label	label used to identify source (independent of	"GPCP" See Appendix 2	ODS2.1	CV with registered content	always	This should be the same as source_id, but without a version number. It will likely be

obs4MIPs global attributes see note 1	Description	Examples	Introduced	Form see note 2	Required	Further information
	source version)					used in faceted searches to get a truncated list of sources (without all the different versions listed)
source_type	Observational class	'satellite_retrieval', 'satellite_blended', "gridded_insitu", "insitu", "reanalysis", "ungridded_insitu", "AI_upscaling"	ODS2.1	CV See Appendix 2	always	See obs4MIPs_source_type.json . New entries added for ODS2.6
source_version_number	Numeric version identifier	v1.0, 1.2 ver2.3.1 See Appendix 2	ODS2.1	CV with registered content	always	See obs4MIPs_source_id.json and search for source_version_number
title	see note 4	see note 4	ODS1.0	free form	optional	no change; CF-convention standard, useful for plotting routines
tracking_id	unique file identifier (automatically generated by CMOR)	see note 14	ODS2.1	structured form with some CV	always	Form modified to facilitate use by ESGF
units_metadata	Defines whether a unit is on-scale or difference or unknown	E.g. "specific_humidity: difference", temperature: on_scale",	NEW IN ODS2.6	structured form with some CV	as appropriate	For anomaly datasets See the CF Conventions documentation Section 3.1

obs4MIPs global attributes see note 1	Description	Examples	Introduced	Form see note 2	Required	Further information
		“temperature: unknown” See Appendix 6				
variable_id	variable identifier	“tas”, “pr”, “ua” Note: anomalies should follow CMIP6 variable_ids with the suffix ‘anom’ e.g., ‘hussanom’, ‘hursanom’, ‘tasanom’ etc. See Appendix 6 for examples of anomaly fields.	ODS1.0 Refined in ODS2.6	CV, new variables and those with the ‘anom’ suffix will need to be added to CV.	always	Added to direct users and software to the primary variable of interest in the file. The complete list of CMIP6 variable_ids is here
variant_info	description of “3rd party” identifier and if applicable run variant	“Best Estimate”, “Sphere of influence = 20km” See note 15	ODS2.1 refined in ODS2.5	free form	as appropriate	Provides a brief description of who has prepared the obs4MIPs-compliant data (e.g., original data curator or a 3rd party). Also, if describing an observational ensemble, variant differences can be described.
variant_label	“variant” label	“PCMDI” Ensemble: examples: “RSS-BE” “RSS-r1”	ODS2.1 refined in ODS2.5	structured form	always	Attribute serving two purposes: 1). a registered institution_id representing where the obs4MIPs product was prepared (either the

obs4MIPs global attributes see note 1	Description	Examples	Introduced	Form see note 2	Required	Further information
		See note 16				<p>institute of the data curator or a 3rd party), AND, if applicable, a concatenated (“-”) 2nd entry to identify a member of an observational ensemble.</p> <p>If there is a default version of an ensemble, it is identified as a ‘best estimate’ or “BE.” The ensemble entry is relevant only when there are multiple estimates of the same source_id (e.g., constructed with alternate processing choices), in which case ensemble member identification could follow CMIP6, e.g., with “BE”, “r1”, “r2”, “r3”, ...</p>

Table Notes:

1. When using CMOR, an additional global attribute will be included: `cmor_version`, *but this is not an obs4MIPs required global attribute*.
2. “CV” means content must be taken from a “controlled vocabulary” defined in coordination with the WIP. “registered content” (RC) is special controlled vocabulary defined by data contributors and monitored by the obs4MIPs Steering Panel. Data contributors can submit RC at (<https://github.com/PCMDI/obs4MIPs-cmor-tables>) and contact submissions-obs4mips@wcrp-cmip.org

3. For backwards compatibility with ODS1.0 project_id will be an alias of activity_id on ESGF.
4. Since some software uses the 'title' for default plotting or describing the contents of a file, it can be used to provide a description that is similar or equivalent to the source. A common entry may be the same as the source but without the release_year.
5. creation_date form: YYYY-MM-DDTHH:MM:SSZ (e.g., "2025-03-23T05:56:23Z").
7. The "grid" global attribute can be used to describe the horizontal grid and re-gridding procedure. There is no standard form used to record this information, but it is suggested that, when appropriate, the following be indicated: brief description of native grid and resolution, and if data have been re-gridded, re-gridding procedure and description of target grid. Here are some examples:

grid = "data re-gridded to a CMIP6 standard 1x1 degree latxlon grid from the native T63 grid using an area-average preserving method"
grid = "data re-gridded via bilinear interpolation to a 3x3 deg latxlon grid from the native atmosphere T63 gaussian grid (64x128 latxlon)"
grid = "data re-gridded to a CMIP6 standard 1x1 degree latxlon grid from the native T63 grid using an area-average preserving method"
grid = "data regridded via bilinear interpolation to a 3x3 deg latxlon grid from the native atmosphere T63 gaussian grid (64x128 latxlon)"
8. Data providers may choose to report their output on one or more grids or, with special care, provide an alternate projection. To distinguish between output reported on different grids, a "grid_label" attribute is defined. The original grid should be labelled with "gn." Additional grids should be labelled using the form "gr[i]" where i is a positive integer. If the data are subsequently re-gridded to a second and third grid, "gr2" and "gr3" could be used to distinguish these grids from "gr1".
9. A description and examples of the contact, comment, history, and references global attributes may be found in the [CMIP6_output_metadata_requirements](#).
10. The "exploratory_product" will be used to include products that are not closely aligned with CMIP model output but have potential value for model evaluation. More information on this will follow.
13. The wording of the "license" attribute is up to the dataset creator, but it is recommended that you reference one of the "Creative Commons" licenses. For example: "Data in this file produced by <Your Centre Name> is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-

4.0 International (**CC BY 4.0**) License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>). Use of the data must be acknowledged following guidelines found at <a URL maintained by you>. Further information about this data, including some limitations, can be found via <some URL maintained by you>.”

14. tracking_id should be of the form hdl:21.14102/<uuid> (e.g., “hdl:21.14102/02d9e6d5-9467-382e-8f9b-9300a64ac3cd”). The tracking_id should be unique for each file published in ESGF. CMOR automatically generates a tracking_id. You can review the python built-in UUID library documentation [here](#).

15. Except when variant_label=“BE”, it is recommended that variant_info include information identifying major distinguishing features of a variant, but care should be taken to record correct information.

16. Via [an obs4MIPs institution_id](#), the variant_label identifies where the obs4MIPs-compliant data was prepared. If an obs4MIPs product is being prepared by the original curators of the source data, the institution_id for the dataset will be the same as the institution_id identified in the source_label. If the obs4MIPs product is prepared by a “3rd party” they will typically be different. Also, if the same source_id is being used to represent multiple versions of an observational “ensemble,” the variant_label can be combined (via “-”) with labels representing subsequent versions. If there is a default or official member, “BE” can be used to identify this best-estimate, with labels representing subsequent versions (derived from different processing choices), with the CMIP nomenclature recommended: ‘BE’, ‘r1’, ‘r2’, ‘r3’... ‘rN’. Examples: “PCMDI”, “RSS-BE”, “RSS-r1”

Data Reference Syntax (DRS) components:

The DRS is used, for example, in file names, directory structures, and in facets of some search tools. The following components are needed for obs4MIPs:

activity_id (original obs4MIPs "activity")
realm (original obs4MIPs "activity")
frequency (original obs4MIPs: "frequency")
product (original obs4MIPs: "product")
institution_id (original obs4MIPs: "institute")
source_id (original obs4MIPs: "model")
source_label (new in obs4MIPs ODS2.1)
variable_id (original obs4MIPs: "variable name")
region (new in obs4MIPs ODS2.1)
grid_label (new in obs4MIPs ODS2.1)
variant_label (original obs4MIPs: "ensemble member")
[version](#) (original obs4MIPs: "version number")

File name template:

The obs4MIPs file name must be consistent with the following template.

obs4MIPs file name template =

<variable_id>_<frequency>_<source_id>_<variant_label>_<grid_label>[_<time_range>].nc

e.g., siconc_mon_OSI-SAF-450-a-3-0_PCMDI-BE_gr1_185001-202301.nc

For time-invariant fields, the last segment (time_range) above is omitted.

All strings appearing in the file name are constructed using only the following characters: a-z, A-Z, 0-9, and the hyphen ("-"), except the hyphen must not appear in `variable_id`. Underscores are prohibited throughout except as shown in the template.

Note that the last segment of the file name indicates the time-range spanned by the data in the file, and is omitted when inappropriate. The format for this segment is the same as in CMIP6 (see Table 2 of the CMIP6 specs document: <http://goo.gl/v1drZl>).

For comparison, here is the CMIP6 file name template:

```
<variable_id>_<table_id>_<source_id>_<experiment_id>_<member_id>_<grid_label>[_<time_range>].nc
```

and the legacy obs4MIPs file name template:

```
<variable>_<instrument>_<processing_level>_<processing_version>_<start_date>-<end_date>.nc
```

Directory structure template:

The obs4MIPs directory structure must be consistent with the following template.

obs4MIPs directory structure =

```
<activity_id>/  
  <institution_id>/  
    <source_id>/  
      <frequency>/  
        <variable_id>/  
          <nominal_resolution>/  
            <version>
```

Any spaces in nominal_resolution are removed in directory structure.

For comparison, here is the CMIP6 directory structure:

```
<mip_era>/  
  <activity_id>/  
    <institution_id>/  
      <source_id>/  
        <experiment_id>/  
          <member_id>/  
            <table_id>/  
              <variable_id>/  
                <grid_label>/  
                  <version>
```

and the legacy obs4MIPs directory structure:

```
obs4MIPs/  
  observations/  
    <realm>/  
      <variable_id>/  
        <frequency>/  
          <grid>/  
            <Institution_id>  
              <instrument>/  
                <version>/
```

Note: <version> here refers to the CMOR-assigned version number which has the form “vYYYYMMDD” (e.g., “v20170921”), indicating a representative date for when the version was produced for obs4MIPs. For those not using CMOR, the convention must be followed.

Sample file header

The example below was produced from the following demo: <https://github.com/PCMDI/obs4MIPs-cmor-tables/demo>

KEY: **BOLD** identifies required global attributes for obs4MIPs compliance.

```
ncdump -h rlut_mon_CERES-EBAF-4-2_RSS_gn_200003-202310.nc  
netcdf rlut_mon_CERES-EBAF-4-2_RSS_gn_200003-202310 {  
  dimensions:  
    time = UNLIMITED ; //(284 currently)  
    lat = 180 ;  
    lon = 360 ;  
    bnds = 2 ;  
  variables:  
    double time(time) ;  
    time:bounds = "time_bnds" ;
```

```
time:units = "days since 2000-03-01 00:00:00" ;
time:calendar = "gregorian" ;
time:axis = "T" ;
time:long_name = "time" ;
time:standard_name = "time" ;
double time_bnds(time, bnds) ;
double lat(lat) ;
lat:bounds = "lat_bnds" ;
lat:units = "degrees_north" ;
lat:axis = "Y" ;
lat:long_name = "Latitude" ;
lat:standard_name = "latitude" ;
double lat_bnds(lat, bnds) ;
double lon(lon) ;
lon:bounds = "lon_bnds" ;
lon:units = "degrees_east" ;
lon:axis = "X" ;
lon:long_name = "Longitude" ;
lon:standard_name = "longitude" ;
double lon_bnds(lon, bnds) ;
float rlut(time, lat, lon) ;
rlut:standard_name = "toa_outgoing_longwave_flux" ;
rlut:long_name = "TOA Outgoing Longwave Radiation" ;
rlut:comment = "at the top of the atmosphere (to be compared with satellite measurements)" ;
rlut:units = "W m-2" ;
rlut:cell_methods = "area: time: mean" ;
rlut:cell_measures = "area: areacella" ;
rlut:history = "2024-03-28T20:04:26Z altered by CMOR: replaced missing value flag (-999) and corresponding data with standard missing value (1e+20).";
rlut:missing_value = 1.e+20f ;
```

```
rlut:_FillValue = 1.e+20f ;  
rlut:valid_min = "0.00000" ;  
rlut:valid_max = "400.000" ;
```

```
    // global attributes:  
:Conventions = "CF-1.11; ODS-2.5" ;  
:aux_uncertainty_id = "ustd" ;  
:activity_id = "obs4MIPs" ;  
:contact = "RSS (support@remss.com)" ;  
:creation_date = "2024-03-28T20:04:26Z" ;  
:data_specs_version = "ODS-2.5" ;  
:doi = "https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-219" ;  
:dataset_contributor = "Andrew I. Manaster" ;  
:external_variables = "areacella" ;  
:frequency = "mon" ;  
:grid = "1x1 degree latitude x longitude" ;  
:grid_label = "gn" ;  
:has_aux_unc = "TRUE" ;  
:history = "2024-03-28T20:04:26Z; CMOR rewrote data to be consistent with obs4MIPs, and CF-1.11; ODS-2.5 standards" ;  
:institution = "NASA-LaRC (Langley Research Center) Hampton, Va" ;  
:institution_id = "NASA-LaRC" ;  
:nominal_resolution = "100 km" ;  
:processing_code_location = "https://github.com/PCMDI/obs4MIPs-cmor-tables/tree/9876ae84146244a20fb498f2a2be7e8272a3142f//inputs/RSS/NASA-LaRC" ;  
:product = "observations" ;  
:realm = "atmos" ;  
:references = "doi: 10.1175/JCLI-D-17-0208.1" ;  
:region = "global" ;  
:site_id = "CA-Gro" ;  
:site_location = "Ontario, Groundhog River, Boreal mixed wood forest" ;
```

```
:source = "CERES-EBAF-4-2 4.2 (2022): CERES EBAF (Energy Balanced and Filled) TOA Fluxes. Monthly Averages" ;
:source_data_retrieval_date = "20230209" ;
:source_data_url = "https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov/data/" ;
:source_id = "CERES-EBAF-4-2" ;
:source_label = "CERES-EBAF-4-2" ;
:source_type = "satellite_blended" ;
:source_version_number = "4.2" ;
:table_id = "obs4MIPs_Amon" ;
:table_info = "Creation Date:(18 November 2020) MD5:6eb29c0516f0c480b52815b28b3cf029" ;
:title = "CERES V4.2 (ODS-v2.5.0)" ;
:tracking_id = "hdl:21.14102/9ba3c901-9094-43c9-b993-54fed1bbf8cb" ;
:variable_id = "rlut" ;
:variant_info = "obs4MIPs-compliant product prepared by RSS" ;
:variant_label = "RSS" ;
:license = "Data in this file produced by NASA-LaRC are licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). Use of the data must be acknowledged following guidelines found at https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov/. Further information about this data, including some limitations, can be found via https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov/." ;
:cmor_version = "3.7.3" ;
:_NCProperties = "version=2,netcdf=4.9.2,hdf5=1.14.2" ;
}
```

Appendix 1: Coordinate bounds

While climate models have grid cells with boundaries that have exact definitions allowing analysts to precisely compute area integrals averages, they are often not well defined for gridded observational products. However, to objectively compare simulations and observations, the area associated with each gridded value in an observational product must be estimated. We therefore recommend that the data provider include their own estimates of the latitude-longitude grid cell bounds from which the grid cell areas can be calculated (since they are most familiar with the data). This will help ensure uniformity among different researchers analysing the data.

Appendix 2: Guidance for defining and registering source information (product description)

We need seven pieces of information from obs4MIPs data providers to enable search functioning and other services on ESGF. (Note that we are referring here to only the “source” information which is collectively used to identify a dataset; data providers will also need to register their institution, and if they are contributing a new variable, not defined in CMIP6, they will need to register the variable). The seven attributes are listed below, each with three examples:

1. **source_name** "brand name" of the dataset (See below for further guidance) e.g.

"REMSS PRW"

"GPCP"

"NOAA NCEI AVHRR NDVI"

2. **release_year** year this version of the data was produced and made available. (The year data were reformatted for obs4MIPs is irrelevant) e.g.

"2017"

"2003"

"2013"

3. **source_description** of the dataset, an expansion of the acronyms or abbreviations appearing in source_name e.g.

"Remote Sensing Systems precipitable water"

"Global Precipitation Climatology Project"

"NOAA Nat Cent ... AVHRR Normalized difference vegetation index"

4. **source_version_number** of the dataset following whatever convention the data provider prefers e.g.

"V6.6.0"

"2.3"

"V4.0"

5. **institution_id** acronym(s) used to identify the institution, group, or consortium responsible for producing the data set e.g.

"RSS"

"UofMD"

"NOAA NCEI"

6. the **region** covered by the dataset (see [obs4MIPs_region.json](#)) the smallest appropriate region among the options should be used e.g.

"global"

"global_ocean"

"global_land"

7. the **source_type** (see [obs4MIPs_source_type.json](#) for options)

"gridded_insitu"

"satellite_blended"

"satellite_retrieval"

From the information above, the obs4MIPs team constructs the following three items:

8. **source_label** = <source_name>, but substituting "-" for certain forbidden characters (including ".", "_", "(", ")", "/", and " ") e.g.

"REMSS-PRW"

"GPCP"

"NOAA-NCEI-AVHRR-NDVI"

9. **source_id** = <source_label>-<source_version_number> but substituting "-" for certain forbidden characters (including ".", "_", "(", ")", "/", and " ") e.g.

"REMSS-PRW-6-6-0"

"GPCP-2-3"

"NOAA-NCEI-AVHRR-NDVI-4-0"

10. **source** = <source_name> <source_version_number> (<release_year>): <source_description> e.g.

"REMSS PRW v6.6.0 (2017): Remote Sensing Systems precipitable water"

"GPCP 2.3 (2003): Global Precipitation Climatology Project"

"NOAA NCEI AVHRR NDVI v4.0 (2013): NOAA Nat Cent ... AVHRR Normalized difference vegetation index"

In summary, data providers must *register content* for the following:

- source_name,
- release_year,
- source_description,
- source_version_number,
- institution_id,
- region,
- source_type.

They can do this by submitting an issue on the [obs4MIPs-cmor-tables github repository](#). From this information the source_label, source_id, and source are constructed. CMOR will record as global attributes all items except the first three; : source_name, release_year, and source_description because they are included in "source" **Notes:**

- The *source_name* must be unique across all obs4MIPs datasets. It should be as short as possible because it appears in file names, directory structures, and search lists.
- For an existing dataset that is being prepared for obs4MIPs, the *source_name* might be an established name associated with the dataset and recognizable by the community (e.g., GPCP, GHCN). For new datasets that do not have a recognized brand name, *source_name* might include an acronym with some indication of who the data provider is, what instrument the observations are based on, and/or the name of the observed variable. The *source_name* should not be too generic because each separate contribution to obs4MIPs (now and in future) must have a unique source_name. For example, if you are contributing a sea surface temperature dataset, but later expect to prepare a sea surface salinity dataset, you should anticipate this when constructing your source_name. You would not want the source_name to simply be the name of your group. Similarly, you would not want your source name to simply be the name of the variable because it is likely other groups will also want to contribute the same variable to obs4MIPs. Consider what name you would like the dataset to be known by in the years to come.
- If an obs4MIPs contribution includes multiple, related datasets (i.e., more than one variable), coming, for example, from a self-consistent analysis procedure, then all the variables would normally share a common source_name and source_version_number.

- If a single group plans to prepare multiple *unrelated* datasets, then each dataset should be assigned a different source_label. By "unrelated" we mean these datasets would normally be independently assigned "release" (or version) numbers. If these multiple, unrelated datasets each deal with a different variable, then one option would be to include the variable name as part of the source_label, but this is not a requirement. The provider might have other ways to distinguish between these datasets.

If a minor problem is found in obs4MIPs datasets (e.g., a mistake in one of the global attributes), the mistake can be corrected without issuing a new "release" with a new version. The data can be republished on ESGF, and ESGF's versioning system will hide the deprecated file(s) and make it easy for users to determine whether they have the most up-to-date files.

Appendix 3: Site (in-situ) data

Until recently, obs4MIPs focused on gridded products for model evaluation. As model-grid granularity has improved, comparison with high-frequency site data becomes increasingly useful. Via [CFMIP](#), a collection of global locations have been identified (cf-sites). Modellers have been asked to provide fields at these locations for comparison.

When high frequency model output is stored at the cf-sites, time-series at all locations have the identical time coordinate, making it practical to CMORise them as a 2-d array (time x site) and save in a single file. By contrast, measurements at different stations do not in general span common time periods. To address this, two pathways can now be used to include site data in obs4MIPs. The first accommodates data from individual sites as distinct datasets. The second enables combining a set of these distinct datasets into a *site-collection* that is harmonized (likely through additional processing) to enable data from each site to be represented with the same time coordinate, yielding a collection that can be provided as a 2-d array (time, site) dataset. In both cases, there are no changes to the core ODS filename and directory templates defined above, only the following modifications:

Individual site

<product>: site-observations

<nominal_resolution>, <grid> and <grid_label> are set to 'site'

(new option for DRS global attribute <product>)

(refined use of attributes in filename and directory templates)

Inclusion of two new infile global attributes¹:

<site_id> Acronym and [locations with lon and lat scalar coordinates](#) without bounds.

<site_location> (e.g., South Western Great Plains) and <site_id> (e.g., SGP) will be curated as part of obs4MIPs CVs
CF regions still honoured for <region>; site location within region selected.

[Demo code based on ARM with sample output](#)

Sample File Header for individual site:

```
netcdf pr_1hr_ARMBE-atm-c1-1-8_LLNL_US-ARM-SGP_201801010030-201807280730 {
dimensions:
    time = UNLIMITED ; // (5000 currently)
    lat = 1 ;
    lon = 1 ;
    bnds = 2 ;
variables:
    double time(time) ;
        time:bounds = "time_bnds" ;
        time:units = "days since 2018-01-01" ;
        time:calendar = "gregorian" ;
        time:axis = "T" ;
        time:long_name = "time" ;
        time:standard_name = "time" ;
    double time_bnds(time, bnds) ;
    double lat(lat) ;
        lat:units = "degrees_north" ;
        lat:axis = "Y" ;
        lat:long_name = "Latitude" ;
```

```
    lat:standard_name = "latitude" ;
double lon(lon) ;
    lon:units = "degrees_east" ;
    lon:axis = "X" ;
    lon:long_name = "Longitude" ;
    lon:standard_name = "longitude" ;
float pr(time, lat, lon) ;
    pr:standard_name = "precipitation_flux" ;
    pr:long_name = "Precipitation" ;
    pr:comment = "includes both liquid and solid phases" ;
    pr:units = "kg m-2 s-1" ;
    pr:cell_methods = "area: time: mean" ;
    pr:cell_measures = "area: areacella" ;
    pr:missing_value = 1.e+20f ;
    pr:_FillValue = 1.e+20f ;

// global attributes:
:Conventions = "CF-1.7 ODS-2.1" ;
:activity_id = "obs4MIPs" ;
:contact = "zhang40@llnl.gov, obs4MIPs-admin@llnl.gov" ;
:creation_date = "2025-09-23T19:27:00Z" ;
:data_specs_version = "2.1.0" ;
:external_variables = "areacella" ;
:frequency = "1hr" ;
:further_info_url = "https://furtherinfo.es-doc.org/obs4MIPs.DOE-ARM.source_labelARMBE-atm-c1-1-8.pr" ;
:grid = "site" ;
:grid_label = "US-ARM-SGP" ;
:history = "2025-09-23T19:27:00Z ; CMOR rewrote data to be consistent with CMIP6, CF-1.7 ODS-2.1 and CF standards." ;
:institution = "U.S. Department of Energy, Atmospheric Radiation Measurement Program" ;
:institution_id = "DOE-ARM" ;
```

```
:mip_era = "CMIP6" ;
:nominal_resolution = "site" ;
:originData_URL = "?" ;
:originData_retrieved = "Chengzhu Zhang 2023" ;
:original_history = "{}" ;
:product = "site-observations" ;
:realm = "atmos" ;
:references = "Xie, Shaocheng., and 16-coauthors, 2010: ARM climate modeling best estimate data, Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc,
91, 13-20 , doi:10.1175/2009BAMS2891.1." ;
:region = "north_america" ;
:site_id = "US-ARM-SGP" ;
:site_location = "Southern Great Plains" ;
:source = "ARMBE atm-c1-1-8 (2023): DOE ARM Best Estimate Data Products for Atmosphere and Cloud properties" ;
:source_id = "ARMBE-atm-c1-1-8" ;
:source_type = "insitu" ;
:source_version_number = "atm-c1-1-8" ;
:table_id = "obs4MIPs_A1hrPt" ;
:table_info = "Creation Date:(18 November 2020) MD5:9ce720238f2a5bdb7d5f590423223263" ;
:title = "ARM Best Estimate (ARMBE) Product, atmospheric profiles: armbeatm" ;
:tracking_id = "42c4bae3-f2a5-45c4-b04b-482dc0279168" ;
:variable_id = "pr" ;
:variant_info = "Best Estimate" ;
:variant_label = "LLNL" ;
:license = "Data in this file is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License
(https://creativecommons.org/licenses)." ;
:cmor_version = "3.9.0" ;
```

data:

Multiple sites

<product>: site-collection (multiple sites with identical time coordinate)
<nominal_resolution>, <grid> and <grid_label> are set to 'site-collection'
templates)

(refined use of attributes in filename and directory

<site_id>: collection

<site_location>:collection

Site-collection provided as 2-d array (time, location), analogous to CFMIP cf-sites; see [CF-compliance](#)

Although not available at time of publication of ODS2.6, a ["site-collection" demo is expected here](#).

Sample File Header for multiple sites example: a group of stations, with one variable, reported hourly, using missing data flags as appropriate rather than compressed time axes. Items in bold are required by ODS2.6.

dimensions:

```
station = 9000 ; // measurement locations  
time = UNLIMITED ;
```

variables:

```
float tas(station, time);  
tas:standard_name = "air temperature";  
tas:coordinates = "lat lon altitude station_id station_name";  
tas:_FillValue = 1.e+20f;  
tas:missing_value = 1.e+20f;  
tas:comment = "near-surface (~2m) observation from weather station with quality control applied";  
tas:units = "K";  
tas:cell_methods = "area: time:point";  
tas:history = "2025-08-20T11:45:26Z altered by CMOR: converted degrees celsius to Kelvin, replaced missing value flag (-1.e+30f and -2.e+30f with standard missing value (1.e+20).";  
tas:valid_min = "0.00000";
```

```
tas:valid_max = "363.00";
double time(time);
time:standard_name = "time";
time:long_name = "time of measurement";
time:units = "hours since 1901-01-01 00:00:00";
time:calendar = "gregorian";
time:axis = "T";
float lon(station);
lon:standard_name = "longitude";
lon:long_name = "station longitude";
lon:units = "degrees_east";
lon:axis = "X";
float lat(station);
lat:standard_name = "latitude";
lat:long_name = "station latitude";
lat:units = "degrees_north";
lat:axis = "Y";
float altitude(station);
altitude:long_name = "vertical distance above the surface";
altitude:standard_name = "height";
altitude:units = "m";
altitude:positive = "up";
altitude:axis = "Z";
string station_id(station);
station_id:long_name = "station identification code";
station_id:cf_role = "timeseries_id";
string station_name(station);
station_name:long_name = "station name";
station_name:cf_role = "timeseries_id";
attributes:
  :featureType = "timeSeries";

// global attributes:
:Conventions = "CF-1.11; ODS-2.6";
```

```
:aux_uncertainty_id = ""; [NB: Only required if :has_aux_unc = "TRUE"]
:activity_id = "obs4MIPs";
:contact = "Met Office, UK (enquiries@metoffice.gov.uk)";
:creation_date = "2025-08-20T11:45:26Z";
:data_specs_version = "ODS-2.6";
:doi = "https://doi.org/xx.xxxx/xxxxxxxx";
:dataset_contributor = "Forename Surname";
:frequency = "1hr";
:grid = "site-collection";
:grid_label = "site-collection";
:has_aux_unc = "FALSE";
:history = "2025-08-10T11:45:26Z; CMOR rewrote data to be consistent with obs4MIPs, and CF-1.11; ODS-2.6 standards";
:institution = "Met Office, UK";
:institution_id = "MOHC";
:nominal_resolution = "site-collection";
:processing_code_location = "https://github.com/PCMDI/obs4MIPs-cmor-tables/tree/xxxxx/inputs/MOHC/MOHC";
:product = "site-collection";
:realm = "atmos";
:references = "doi: xx.xxxx/xxxxxxxx";
:region = "global";
:site_id = "collection";
:site_location = "collection";
:source = "Met Office Hadley Centre's Integrated Surface Dataset of hourly observations";
:source_data_retrieval_date = "20250801";
:source_data_url = "https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/hadisd/ and
https://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/f579035b3c954475922e4b13705a7669/ ";
:source_id = "HadISD";
:source_label = "HadISD-3-4-1-2024f";
:source_type = "ungridded_insitu";
```

```
:source_version_number = "3.4.1.2024f";  
:table_id = "obs4MIPs_Amon";  
:table_info = "Creation Date:(18 November 2020) MD5:6eb29c0516f0c480b52815b28b3cf029";  
:title = "HadISD3.4.1.2024f (ODS-v2.6.0)";  
:tracking_id = "xxxxxx";  
:variable_id = "tas";  
:variant_info = "obs4MIPs-compliant product prepared by MOHC";  
:variant_label = "MOHC";  
:license = "Data in this file produced by MOHC are licensed under a Non-commercial Government License  
(https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/non-commercial-government-licence/version/2//). Use of the data must be acknowledged  
following guidelines found at https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/hadisd/. Further information about this data, including some  
limitations, can be found via https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/hadisd/." ;  
:cmor_version = "x.x.x" ; (NOTE: this will be defined at point of cmorising)
```

Appendix 4: Data preparation

[Instructional](#) documentation and [demos](#) are available along with the codes used to prepare existing products.

The institution preparing the obs4MIPs-compliant data is identified in the <variant_label> and can be the same institution where the data is curated (i.e., same as institution_id) or a third-party institution that is [registered with obs4MIPs](#).

For a dataset to be obs4MIPs-compliant it must:

- Have the <source_id> registered on the obs4MIPs GitHub (GH) repo along with the other required registered content.
- Provide code used to make the data obs4MIPs-compliant available on the obs4MIPs GH metadata repo.

The three stages of obs4MIPs data preparation are:

An **obs4MIPs-compliant dataset** is a netCDF file(s) that has been prepared according to all specifications described in this document and on the GH repository mentioned above. This includes submitting the required *registered content* to the repository and including the associated processing codes on the GH repository. Anything short of this may be *obs4MIPs-like*, but not obs4MIPs-compliant.

An **obs4MIPs product** is an obs4MIPs-compliant dataset that has been published to the ESGF obs4MIPs project

A **reviewed obs4MIPs product** is an obs4MIPs-product that has been assessed by the obs4MIPs Steering Panel and has been assigned indicators as described in [Fig 2a of Waliser et al. \(2020\)](#).

Appendix 5: Variable name suffixes for characterising uncertainty

NOTE: The definitions below stem from ongoing community discussions and may be adapted in future versions of ODS. Data contributors are encouraged to use the definitions below that are suitable for describing uncertainty in their data. See the latest information here: <https://zenodo.org/records/17312883>

Uncertainty information can be included as separate files, prepared identically to the analysis variable, differing only in the variable_id which can be modified by appending the appropriate suffix (see table below) to the variable name. For example:

pr_day_GPCP-Daily-3-2_RSS_gn_20000601-20001231.nc (obs4MIPs product)

pnobs_day_GPCP-Daily-3-2_RSS_gn_20000601-20001231.nc (uncertainty information associated with obs4MIPs product)

Uncertainty variable_id suffixes

Suffix	Long name	Description
nobs	Number of observations	The number of discrete observations or measurements from which a data value has been derived.
stderr	Standard error	Legacy term used for backward compatibility. Definition is identical to that of <code>ustd</code> , the standard uncertainty.
sd	Standard deviation	The standard deviation on the mean, legacy term for backwards compatibility.
ustd	Standard uncertainty	The per-datum standard uncertainty is a combination of independent, structured and common effects and is equal to the positive square root of the sum of the components. The standard uncertainty is provided at one standard deviation. Replacement for 'standard error' due to updated terminology.

uind	Uncertainty due to independent effects	The per-datum component of uncertainty that is associated with uncorrelated effects, between observations, provided at one standard deviation.
ustr	Uncertainty due to structured effects	The per-datum component of uncertainty that is structured and correlated over a defined space/time scale, provided at one standard deviation. This correlation length scale in space and time must be provided in the variable metadata.
ucom	Uncertainty due to common effects	The per-datum component of uncertainty that is common to all observations of a given type (specific instrument, resolution, variable type) at one standard deviation. The definition of the type of measurement for which this uncertainty is common should be provided in the variable metadata.
lbnd	Lower bound of asymmetrical uncertainty information	Alternative to <code>stderr</code> and <code>ustd</code> for observations with asymmetrical uncertainty distribution, lower bound of the uncertainty interval.
ubnd	Upper bound of asymmetrical uncertainty information	Alternative to <code>stderr</code> and <code>ustd</code> for observations with asymmetrical uncertainty distribution, upper bound of the uncertainty interval.

Appendix 6: Anomaly Data

Some observational products are best provided as anomalies rather than actual values. This is because they are derived from uneven/sparse point locations, with missing data, which can lead to substantial sampling biases in gridded and regionally aggregated quantities. Comparing actual values from such datasets with model fields is not a fair test on the models. The use of anomalies (differences from a long-term [e.g., 30 year] mean) reduces these biases substantially, especially for variables with long correlation decay distances like temperature and humidity. However, users need to know that they are working with anomalies, and also the reference period from which the anomalies are derived.

We require obs4MIPs anomaly datasets to add 'anom' to the relevant CMIP6 variable_id to define that the data are anomalies. We also require the dataset to state the climatological reference period within the long_name.

Where there is an anomaly standard name (e.g., air_temperature_anomaly, surface_temperature_anomaly - see: <https://cfconventions.org/Data/cf-standard-names/current/build/cf-standard-name-table.html>) this should also be used, and in cases the appropriate anomaly standard name is not listed in CF, the dataset preparer is encouraged to [submit a proposal to have it added to CF](#).

The units_metadata attribute should also be used to clarify that the quantity is a difference value rather than an on scale value (e.g., units_metadata="specific_humidity: difference". See Section 3.1 - <https://cfconventions.org/Data/cf-conventions/cf-conventions-1.12/cf-conventions.pdf>).

Example:

hussanom_mon_HadISDH-land-4-61-2024f_MOHC_gn_19730101-20241231.nc (obs4MIPs product)

variables:

float hussanom;

hussanom:long_name="near-surface (2m) specific humidity monthly mean anomaly from the 1991-2020 climatological reference period"

hussanom:units="hPa";

hussanom:units_metadata="specific_humidity: difference";

hussanom:cell_methods="time: mean over station month, area: mean over gridbox" (optional)

Appendix 7: Document version information

0.1 (23 October, 2016) - Document initiated with CMIP6 analog. *Not public.*

0.2 (23 October - 22 February 2017) - working on draft document in relation to CMIP6, CMIP5 and original obs4MIPs specs.

0.3 (March 01 - April 05 2017) - Added “region” as global attribute, finessing Table 1 footnotes.

0.4 (April 25, 2017) - Draft made public on obs4MIPs CoG site enabling broader feedback.

[2.0 released \(June 30, 2017\)](#) on obs4MIPs CoG site.

[2.1 \(June 25, 2017\)](#) - update made public on obs4MIPs CoG site.

[2.5 Released April 15, 2024](#) - improves provenance and version control via the addition or modification of selected attributes.

2.6 Released September 30, 2025 - introduces protocol for in-situ data, uncertainties, anomaly data and additional global attributes.

2.6.1 Release November 25, 2025 - updates uncertainties nomenclature and descriptions.

Note: As of November 2024, CoG is no longer available as an interface to ESGF. It has been superseded by [Metagrid](#).